

Adsorptive removal of pharmaceutical contaminants: accurate description of tailing breakthrough curves

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Abstract

Fixed bed adsorption is a well-established method used to remove various contaminants, including pharmaceuticals, from aqueous solutions. Mathematical modeling plays a pivotal role in analyzing the dynamic behavior of fixed bed adsorption processes. The classic Bohart–Adams model, dating back over a century, is commonly used to describe fixed bed breakthrough curves. However, it encounters difficulties in effectively interpreting tailing breakthrough curves resulting from the slow approach of the fixed bed to saturation. This study presents an enhanced version of the Bohart–Adams model, specifically tailored to address the challenge of analyzing tailing breakthrough data concerning pharmaceutical contaminant adsorption in fixed bed adsorbers. The new formulation incorporates a conceptual steric hindrance model, proposing that the tailing breakthrough behavior is a consequence of a reduction in the rate of adsorption as surface coverage increases. Through rigorous testing, the new model showcased superior performance compared to the original model, accurately describing the tailing breakthrough curves commonly observed with pharmaceutical contaminants such as diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, and tetracycline. Additionally, comparative analyses of the new model, a mechanistic model, and the empirical Yan model conclusively demonstrated the superiority of the newly proposed approach. The new Bohart–Adams model can be used to precisely predict breakthrough and exhaustion times or optimize column operating conditions.

Keywords: Antibiotic; Asymmetric breakthrough curve; Hindered diffusion; Steric hindrance; Tailing breakthrough curve.

1. Introduction

Fixed bed adsorption is a highly efficient method for eliminating organic micropollutants, including pharmaceutically active compounds, from water. The effectiveness of this approach is assessed through experimental breakthrough curves, which depict the change in contaminant concentration in the effluent stream over time. However, understanding breakthrough behavior proves challenging due to its reliance on several system and operational factors. To methodically analyze the dynamic behavior of fixed bed adsorbers, mathematical models are often used to extract important information, such as breakthrough and exhaustion times, from breakthrough data collected under different conditions.

Most of the mathematical models used to investigate gas adsorption in fixed beds are founded on mass transfer principles [1]. However, in the realm of aqueous phase adsorption, the Bohart–Adams model, which is based on a reaction kinetic mechanism, has emerged as a prominent choice. Originally formulated to study the adsorption of chlorine gas in fixed bed columns [2], the Bohart–Adams model gained considerable recognition when adapted to develop the bed depth-service time design approach for sizing activated carbon columns, specifically in the area of water and wastewater treatment [3,4].

The Bohart–Adams model is well known for its simplicity and user-friendliness, making it a valuable tool for assessing the effectiveness of fixed bed adsorption. However, it does have certain limitations, with one significant constraint being its inability to accurately interpret asymmetric breakthrough curves [5,6]. Such asymmetry is commonly observed in the breakthrough curves of pharmaceutically active compounds and other micropollutants. The primary cause of this asymmetry is the gradual approach of the fixed bed to saturation, often referred to as “tailing.” When challenged with breakthrough data exhibiting a pronounced degree of tailing, the Bohart–Adams model often struggles to fit both the initial and saturation segments adequately, leading to considerable inaccuracies in estimating breakthrough and exhaustion times. Despite this drawback, researchers have employed the Bohart–Adams model to represent breakthrough curves of pharmaceutical contaminants, as shown in Table 1. It should be noted that some of the models listed in Table 1 are capable of describing asymmetric breakthrough curves.

The ability of the Bohart–Adams model to effectively describe tailing breakthrough curves has seen limited improvements, mostly through empirical adjustments to its mathematical structure [5]. In this study, we propose a novel modification to the Bohart–Adams model and assess its performance in describing tailing breakthrough curves related to the adsorption of pharmaceutical contaminants, with a specific focus on diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, and tetracycline. What distinguishes our modified Bohart–Adams model from previous attempts is its solid grounding in physical reasoning, offering a fresh and promising approach to improving the model’s data fitting capability.

Table 1. Modeling of breakthrough curves of pharmaceutically active compounds.^a

Ref.	Pharmaceutical	Fixed bed model
Sotelo et al. [7]	Caffeine; diclofenac	BA
Sotelo et al. [8]	Atenolol; isoproturon	BA; Thomas; YN; Clark; Wolborska
Sotelo et al. [9]	Carbamazepine	BA; Thomas; YN; Clark
Nazari et al. [10]	Cephalexin	BA; Thomas; YN
Álvarez-Torrellas et al. [11]	Ibuprofen; tetracycline	PSD
de Franco et al. [12]	Diclofenac	BA; Thomas; Yan
Zhang et al. [13]	Tetracycline	Thomas
de Andrade et al. [14]	Diclofenac; losartan	Thomas; YN; Yan; ILE; dual-site LDF
Antonelli et al. [15]	Ofloxacin	Thomas; YN; Yan; Clark
Wang et al. [16]	Tetracycline	Yan
Vera et al. [17]	Acetaminophen	BA; Thomas; YN; Yan; Wolborska; Wang; LDF
Puga et al. [18]	Venlafaxine; trazodone; fluoxetine	Thomas; YN; Yan
Yu et al. [19]	Tetracycline	YN
de Araújo et al. [20]	Acetaminophen	BA; Thomas; YN; Yan
Quesada et al. [21]	Caffeine	BA; log-BA; Yan
Sompornpailin et al. [22]	Ibuprofen	Log-Thomas
Juela et al. [23]	Sulfamethoxazole	LDF
Spaolonzi et al. [24]	Cefazolin	Thomas; YN; Yan; dual-site LDF
Silveira-Neto et al. [25]	Paracetamol	BA; Thomas; Yan

^a BA: Bohart–Adams; YN: Yoon–Nelson; PSD: pore and surface diffusion; ILE: instantaneous local equilibrium; LDF: linear driving force.

2. Case studies

In this study, we selected four sets of breakthrough data on pharmaceutical adsorption in fixed bed columns from previously published research. The first set of data was derived from a study conducted by Sotelo et al. [7], examining the adsorption of diclofenac in an activated carbon column. Diclofenac is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug commonly prescribed for pain relief, inflammation reduction, and fever reduction. The experimental details for the selected fixed bed experiment can be found in column 2 of Table 2.

The second set of data was taken from a recent publication by Juela et al. [23], focusing on the adsorption of sulfamethoxazole in a fixed bed column packed with sugarcane bagasse. Sulfamethoxazole is a widely used antibiotic for bacterial infections. The experimental setup for this fixed bed study is outlined in column 3 of Table 2.

The third and fourth sets of data were obtained from studies conducted by Módenes et al. [26] and Wang et al. [16], respectively, both investigating the adsorption of tetracycline in fixed bed columns. The columns were packed with biochar [26] and wheat straw [16]. Tetracycline is a commonly used antibiotic for treating bacterial infections. Columns 4 and 5 of Table 2 describe the experimental conditions for the two fixed bed experiments.

Table 2. Experimental conditions for diclofenac [7], sulfamethoxazole [23], and tetracycline [16,26] adsorption in fixed bed columns.

Parameter	Contaminant			
	Diclofenac [7]	Sulfamethoxazole [23]	Tetracycline [26]	Tetracycline [16]
Adsorbent	Activated carbon	Sugarcane bagasse	Biochar	Wheat straw
Adsorbent diameter (mm)	0.54	0.59	0.3–0.7	–
Column diameter (cm)	0.6	4.4	1	1
Column length (cm)	4	50	20	5
Flow rate (cm ³ min ⁻¹)	2	20	2	6
Superficial velocity (cm min ⁻¹)	7.1	1.3	2.5	7.6
Empty bed contact time (min)	0.6	38	7.9	0.7
Feed concentration (mg cm ⁻³)	0.01	0.005	0.005	0.2

3. Fixed bed models

3.1. The Bohart–Adams model

In this model, the rate of adsorption is described by Eq. (1), which is based on a second-order irreversible kinetic mechanism. Eq. (2) is the mass balance equation for the liquid phase.

In these equations, q is the average contaminant concentration in the adsorbent particles at time t , c is the contaminant concentration in the liquid phase at time t , c_0 is the feed concentration, x is the column axial coordinate, v is the interstitial velocity, ε is the bed voidage, L is the bed length, ρ_p is the adsorbent density, k is the Bohart–Adams rate coefficient, and q_s is the adsorption capacity. In chemical engineering research, the analytical solution to Eqs. (1) and (2) is represented by Eq. (3).

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = kc(q_s - q) \quad (1)$$

$$v \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \rho_p \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{\exp(nT)}{\exp(nT) + \exp(n) - 1} \quad (3)$$

$$T = \frac{c_0}{\rho_p q_s} \left(\frac{vt}{L} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{1-\varepsilon} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$n = \frac{k\rho_p q_s L}{v} \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{\varepsilon} \right) \quad (5)$$

In the field of environmental engineering, Eq. (3) is reformulated as Eq. (6), where q_s is combined with other parameters to yield N , representing the amount of contaminant adsorbed per unit bed volume, and u denotes the superficial velocity [6]. The advantages associated with Eq. (6) are twofold: it obviates the need for knowledge regarding the adsorbent density and bed voidage, and it allows for simple linearization.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(kNL/u - kc_0 t)} \quad (6)$$

It is important to recognize that assuming the kinetics of adsorption as the sole rate-limiting step in the Bohart–Adams model is unrealistic. In the case of physical adsorption, the kinetics of adsorption is generally much faster compared to other mass transfer effects, such as external film mass transfer and pore diffusion. To address this issue, an approximate relation has been identified [6], which combines the external film mass transfer coefficient (k_f) and the pore diffusion coefficient (D_e) into the Bohart–Adams rate coefficient (k). This relation is expressed by Eq. (7), where r_p denotes the adsorbent particle radius. By adopting this approach,

k can be treated as a lumped mass transfer parameter rather than being solely an empirical reaction kinetic coefficient.

$$\frac{1}{k} \cong \frac{r_p^2 \rho_p q_s}{30} \left(\frac{5}{k_f r_p} + \frac{1}{D_e} \right) \quad (7)$$

3.2. Modification of the Bohart–Adams model

Tailing is a commonly observed phenomenon in the fixed bed adsorption of pharmaceutical contaminants. Although there may be other contributing factors, one likely reason is the gradual reduction in the rate of adsorption caused by the obstruction of adsorbed molecules at high surface coverage, which is known as steric hindrance. The slow approach to saturation, resulting from steric hindrance, often leads to pronounced tailing in breakthrough curves. To consider the impact of steric hindrance, a conceptual model proposed by Jin et al. [27] can be used to modify the Bohart–Adams kinetic equation described in Eq. (1). The modified kinetic equation, as defined by Eq. (8), incorporates this steric hindrance effect, where $\theta = q/q_s$ and the coefficients B_1 and B_2 are functions of the relative binding site density [27]. Essentially, the modification entails multiplying the original rate coefficient k by the term $(1 - B_1\theta - B_2\theta^2)^2$. As a result, the rate coefficient decreases as the adsorbent loading q or θ increases.

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = kc(1 - \theta)(1 - B_1\theta - B_2\theta^2)^2 \quad (8)$$

The fixed bed model that incorporates the influence of steric hindrance, as defined by Eqs. (2) and (8), is most conveniently solved using a numerical method. However, it may be possible to account for the influence of steric hindrance by making a judicious adjustment to the analytical solution presented in Eq. (6). Our approach involves the use of two distinct rate coefficients: one that excludes the steric hindrance effect (represented by k_1) and another that incorporates the steric hindrance effect (designated as k_2). In the modified formulation outlined in Eq. (9), k_1 should be significantly larger than k_2 . The ability of Eq. (9) to describe tailing breakthrough curves will be evaluated using the datasets described in Section 2. In this work, Eq. (9) is referred to as the Chu–Hashim model.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k_1 NL/u - k_1 c_0 t) + \exp(-k_2 c_0 t)} \quad (9)$$

3.3. Model fitting and evaluation

The fixed bed models considered in this work were fitted to experimental breakthrough curves using GraphPad Prism's nonlinear regression method. The accuracy of the fitting was evaluated through two statistical metrics: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Akaike weight (AW). The R^2 metric is defined in Eq. (10), where C_{exp} represents the experimental value of c/c_0 , C_{cal} denotes the value of c/c_0 calculated from a fixed bed model, $C_{exp,av}$ is the mean of all C_{exp} values, and z is the number of data points. The AW metric is defined in Eqs. (11)–(14), where SSR denotes the sum of squared residuals, AIC represents the corrected Akaike Information Criterion, p is the number of fitting parameters, AIC_i is the AIC value for the i -th model, AIC_m is the AIC value for the model with the lowest score, and w is the number of competing models. The AW metric offers an estimate of the probability that the model with the lowest AIC value is the correct choice. It facilitates a comparative assessment of fit quality among models that differ in the number of fitting parameters.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^z (C_{exp,i} - C_{cal,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^z (C_{exp,i} - C_{exp,av})^2} \quad (10)$$

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^z (C_{exp,i} - C_{cal,i})^2 \quad (11)$$

$$AIC = z \ln \left(\frac{SSR}{z} \right) + \frac{2z(p+1)}{z-p-2} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta_i = AIC_i - AIC_m \quad (13)$$

$$AW = 100 \frac{\exp(-0.5\Delta_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^w \exp(-0.5\Delta_j)} \quad (14)$$

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Diclofenac adsorption on activated carbon

As mentioned in Section 2, the first dataset pertains to the adsorption of diclofenac in a fixed bed column packed with activated carbon [7]. The experimental conditions are given in

column 2 of Table 2. Fig. 1 displays the selected breakthrough curve, alongside the corresponding modeling results, which will be discussed below. Two noteworthy aspects are worth highlighting: firstly, the empty bed contact time (EBCT) was remarkably short, measuring less than one minute, and secondly, the duration of the experiment lasted approximately 6 days. Observations from pilot-scale studies conducted on activated carbon columns with the objective of eliminating micropollutants, including human pharmaceuticals, from wastewater treatment plant effluents have demonstrated that optimal performance requires a minimum EBCT of 20–30 minutes [28].

Fig. 1. Fitting diclofenac breakthrough data [7] with the Bohart–Adams model [Eq. (6)] and the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)].

Fig. 1 vividly illustrates the asymmetry observed in the diclofenac breakthrough curve. Initially, the curve exhibited a rapid rise, followed by a gradual approach toward but never reaching $c/c_0 = 1.0$, even after running the fixed bed experiment for about 6 days. The Bohart–Adams model fit was very poor ($R^2 = 0.871$), as evidenced by its inability to track the overall shape of the tailing breakthrough curve. Another drawback of the Bohart–Adams model is its tendency to predict a nonzero effluent concentration at $t = 0$ when applied to strongly asymmetric breakthrough data. This can be observed in the diclofenac example, where the model predicted $c/c_0 = 0.12$ at $t = 0$. Consequently, if the breakthrough concentration is below $c/c_0 = 0.12$, the Bohart–Adams model would yield a negative breakthrough time, which is clearly nonsensical.

Fig. 1 illustrates that the Chu–Hashim model provided a significantly better description of the experimental data, yielding a substantially higher R^2 value of 0.995. Furthermore, it predicted an effluent concentration close to zero ($c/c_0 = 0.01$) at $t = 0$. Consequently, the Chu–Hashim model demonstrated clear superiority over the Bohart–Adams model in fitting the diclofenac breakthrough curve. Additionally, Table 3 reveals that the Akaike test rejected the Bohart–Adams model with two fitting parameters (AW = 0%) while endorsing the Chu–Hashim model with three fitting parameters (AW = 100%) as the superior model in terms of performance.

Table 3 presents a summary of the fitted parameters. Notably, a significant discrepancy was observed between the fitted values for the rate coefficients k_1 and k_2 in the Chu–Hashim model, with k_1 being approximately 13 times greater than k_2 . This significant difference in the fitted values played a crucial role in capturing the rapid initial phase of the diclofenac breakthrough curve (attributed to the larger k_1 value) and the gradual tailing segment (attributed to the substantially smaller k_2 value). Despite the steric hindrance model, as described in Eq. (8), suggesting a continuous decrease in the rate coefficient with increasing adsorbent loading, our approach of approximating this gradual decrease using two distinct rate coefficients has proven to be remarkably effective.

Table 3. Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the model fits plotted in Fig. 1.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Bohart–Adams	(6)	N	83.09 (6.77)	R^2	0.871
		k	0.043 (0.007)	AW	0
Chu–Hashim	(9)	N	47.47 (1.01)	R^2	0.995
		k_1	0.163 (0.012)	AW	100
		k_2	0.012 (0.001)		

^a N is in mg cm^{-3} ; k , k_1 , and k_2 are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; AW is in %.

The fitted value for the rate coefficient k in the Bohart–Adams model was bracketed between the fitted values for k_1 and k_2 , as shown in Table 3. However, this intermediate value failed to accurately capture both the sharp initial phase and the gradual tailing portion of the diclofenac breakthrough curve. The data fitting capability of the Bohart–Adams model is hindered by its reliance on a single rate coefficient (k) to track the entire shape of a tailing breakthrough curve. As a result, k must account for both the rapid initial adsorption rate and the slower adsorption rate as the fixed bed approaches saturation, leading to compromises in

representing the entire shape of tailing breakthrough data. It should be noted that the parameter N governs the temporal positioning of a breakthrough curve, exerting minimal influence on its shape.

4.2. Sulfamethoxazole adsorption on sugarcane bagasse

The second case study concerns the adsorption of sulfamethoxazole in a fixed bed column packed with sugarcane bagasse [23]. The experimental conditions are tabulated in column 3 of Table 2. In contrast to the diclofenac case, where a very short EBCT was employed, a more realistic EBCT of 38 minutes was used for this experiment, as shown in Table 2. Similar to the diclofenac breakthrough curve, the breakthrough curve for sulfamethoxazole, depicted in Fig. 2, exhibited an asymmetric shape. Alongside the experimental data, the figure also includes modeling results. Upon examining the experimental data, it becomes evident that the breakthrough curve displayed a sharp rise during the initial breakthrough phase, followed by significant broadening as the fixed bed approached saturation.

In the original study [23], the authors used a mechanistic model to predict the sulfamethoxazole breakthrough curve. This model considered typical transport mechanisms, including axial dispersion, external film mass transfer, and intraparticle diffusion. The latter two mass transfer processes were represented using a linear driving force (LDF) rate expression. Additionally, the Langmuir model was used to account for nonlinear adsorption. To handle the nonlinearity of the Langmuir isotherm, a numerical method was used to solve the model equations. The model parameters were estimated through batch experiments and engineering correlations. However, when comparing the predicted curve with the experimental data, panel A of Fig. 2 demonstrates that only partial agreement was found. The model effectively described the initial rise of the experimental data up to $c/c_0 \approx 0.2$, but beyond this point, it struggled to capture the gradual approach to saturation, overestimating the effluent concentration in the final phase of breakthrough. Notably, the predicted curve exhibited a symmetric profile, failing to replicate the asymmetry observed in the experimental data.

Fig. 2. Modeling sulfamethoxazole breakthrough data [23] with the mechanistic model of the original study (A), the Bohart–Adams model [Eq. (6)] (B), and the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)] (B).

Panel B of Fig. 2 presents a comparison of the fits of the Bohart–Adams and Chu–Hashim models to the experimental data. The Bohart–Adams model provided a poor representation of the experimental data, as evidenced by an R^2 value of 0.912. It failed to accurately describe both the initial rise in the breakthrough curve and the slow approach to saturation. Furthermore, the Bohart–Adams model predicted a nonzero effluent concentration at $t = 0$, deviating from the expected value of zero. In contrast, the Chu–Hashim model precisely captured the initial rise and the gradual approach to saturation, resulting in an impressive R^2 value of 0.998.

Table 4 provides a summary of the fitted parameters and statistical metrics. As indicated by the Akaike test, the Chu–Hashim model achieved a perfect AW score of 100%, signifying its complete superiority over the Bohart–Adams model. Notably, Table 4 reveals a substantial difference between the fitted values for the two rate coefficients in the Chu–Hashim model, with k_1 being approximately 12 times larger than k_2 . The fitted value for k in the Bohart–Adams model was bracketed between the fitted values for k_1 and k_2 . These findings align with the observations from the diclofenac example, providing further confirmation of the consistency and reliability of the Chu–Hashim model.

Table 4. Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the model fits plotted in panel B of Fig. 2.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Bohart–Adams	(6)	N	0.01 (6×10^{-4})	R^2	0.912
		k	6.68 (1.06)	AW	0
Chu–Hashim	(9)	N	0.008 (7×10^{-5})	R^2	0.998
		k_1	23.01 (1.47)	AW	100
		k_2	1.87 (0.05)		

^a N is in mg cm^{-3} ; k , k_1 , and k_2 are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; AW is in %.

4.3. Symmetric and hyperbolic breakthrough curves

The Chu–Hashim model has proven its effectiveness in describing breakthrough data with notable asymmetry and tailing. However, an important question arises regarding its ability to interpret breakthrough data that is highly symmetric. To investigate this issue, we used the Chu–Hashim model to analyze the breakthrough curve presented in Fig. 3. This dataset was obtained from the work of Módenes et al. [26], which investigated the adsorption of tetracycline in a fixed bed column packed with biochar. The experimental details for this fixed bed experiment are provided in column 4 of Table 2. For comparative analysis, we also included the Bohart–Adams model in this case study.

Fig. 3. Fitting tetracycline breakthrough data [26] with the Bohart–Adams model [Eq. (6)] (A) and the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)] (B).

. Based on the visual examination of the experimental data presented in Fig. 3, it appears that the tetracycline breakthrough curve displayed a highly symmetric sigmoid shape. However, it is important to note that breakthrough curves without tailing are uncommon in studies

focusing on the adsorption of pharmaceuticals in fixed bed adsorbers. In panel A of Fig. 3, the tetracycline data was fitted to the Bohart–Adams model. The experimental profile exhibited a high level of agreement with the fit obtained from the Bohart–Adams model, as evidenced by an impressive R^2 score of 0.997. This remarkable performance of the Bohart–Adams model, known for its accurate fitting of symmetric sigmoid curves, effectively validated the symmetry of the data as initially inferred from the visual inspection.

Moving to panel B of Fig. 3, the fitted curve obtained from the Chu–Hashim model is displayed. The Chu–Hashim model accurately tracked the entire tetracycline breakthrough curve, resulting in an almost perfect R^2 value of 0.999. This finding, along with the successful interpretation of previous datasets involving diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole, validated the exceptional efficacy of the Chu–Hashim model in interpreting both symmetric and asymmetric breakthrough data.

Returning to the topic of breakthrough curve asymmetry, it is noteworthy that previous studies investigating the fixed bed adsorption of pharmaceutical contaminants have reported breakthrough curves that deviate from the typical sigmoid patterns. Instead, these curves display pseudo-hyperbolic profiles [16,29]. When breakthrough occurs rapidly, the sharp increase in effluent concentration leads to a breakthrough curve with a pseudo-hyperbolic shape. An example of such a breakthrough curve, obtained from the adsorption of tetracycline on wheat straw [16], is depicted in Fig. 4. The experimental conditions for this fixed bed experiment are tabulated in column 5 of Table 2. Fig. 4 shows that the initial concave upward segment of the breakthrough curve is barely noticeable, creating the illusion of a hyperbolic curve.

Fig. 4. Fitting tetracycline breakthrough data [16] with the Bohart–Adams model [Eq. (6)] (A) and the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)] (B).

In panel A of Fig. 4, the Bohart–Adams model was fitted to the tetracycline breakthrough data, resulting in an R^2 value of 0.916. It is evident from panel A of Fig. 4 that the Bohart–Adams model encountered significant challenges in capturing the pseudo-hyperbolic shape of the experimental curve. Also, panel A of Fig. 4 indicates the presence of a noticeable nonzero effluent concentration at $t = 0$. In contrast, panel B of Fig. 4 shows that the pseudo-hyperbolic shape of the experimental data was effectively captured by the Chu–Hashim model. The fitted curve precisely matched the experimental observations, resulting in a noteworthy R^2 value of 0.997. This finding demonstrates the versatility of the Chu–Hashim model in handling asymmetric breakthrough curves of various shapes and forms.

4.4. Comparing the Yan and Chu–Hashim models

The Yan model is widely recognized for its ability to describe asymmetric breakthrough curves. Hence, comparing the Chu–Hashim and Yan models is of practical interest. Although Yan et al. [30] did not provide specific details regarding the origins of their model, they asserted that it was derived from a dose-response model commonly used in pharmacology. Mathematically, the Yan model is represented by Eq. (15), wherein α and β serve as empirical fitting parameters. As demonstrated by Apiratikul and Chu [5], Eq. (15) can be transformed into Eq. (16), which is equivalent to the well-known Hill equation [31], extensively used in quantitative pharmacology.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + (t/\alpha)^\beta} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{\alpha t^\beta}{1 + \alpha t^\beta} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 5 presents a comparison between the Chu–Hashim and Yan models using the experimental breakthrough curve of diclofenac, which was extracted from Fig. 1. The Chu–Hashim model fit shown in Fig. 5 was also taken from Fig. 1. The parameter estimates and fit statistics for both models can be found in Table 5. It is evident from Fig. 5 that the Yan model fit was notably inferior to the Chu–Hashim model fit, as the latter closely aligned with the experimental observations. Additionally, Table 5 indicates that the standard error for α was greater than the best-fit value, suggesting a lack of uniqueness in the parameter estimate. The Akaike test decisively favored the Chu–Hashim model, providing compelling statistical evidence of its significant superiority over the Yan model.

Fig. 5. Fitting diclofenac breakthrough data [7] with the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)] and the Yan model [Eq. (16)].

Table 5. Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the model fits plotted in Fig. 5.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Chu–Hashim	(9)	N	47.47 (1.01)	R^2	0.995
		k_1	0.163 (0.012)	AW	99.99
		k_2	0.012 (0.001)		
Yan	(16)	α	1.58×10^{-6} (1.7×10^{-6})	R^2	0.975
		β	1.61 (0.13)	AW	0.01

^a N is in mg cm^{-3} ; k , k_1 , and k_2 are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; α is in $\text{min}^{-\beta}$; β is dimensionless; AW is in %.

Next, the sulfamethoxazole breakthrough curve, taken from Fig. 2, was used to compare the Chu–Hashim and Yan models. Fig. 6 showcases the model fits, and the corresponding fitted parameters and fit statistics are presented in Table 6. As observed in Fig. 6, the Yan model fit significantly deviated from the experimental profile, overestimating the effluent concentration in both the initial and final stages of breakthrough. Table 6 indicates that the standard error for α was larger than the best-fit value, revealing another limitation of the Yan model. Despite yielding a relatively high R^2 value of 0.971, the Yan model fit can be misleading since it was completely rejected by the Akaike test (AW = 0%). In contrast, as depicted in Fig. 6, the Chu–Hashim model demonstrated substantial superiority over the Yan model in accurately describing the tailing experimental profile.

Fig. 6. Fitting sulfamethoxazole breakthrough data [23] with the Chu–Hashim model [Eq. (9)] and the Yan model [Eq. (16)].

Table 6. Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the model fits plotted in Fig. 6.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Chu–Hashim	(9)	N	0.008 (7×10^{-5})	R^2	0.998
		k_1	23.01 (1.47)	AW	100
		k_2	1.87 (0.05)		
Yan	(16)	α	1.25×10^{-5} (1.4×10^{-5})	R^2	0.971
		β	2.62 (0.26)	AW	0

^a N is in mg cm^{-3} ; k , k_1 , and k_2 are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; α is in $\text{min}^{-\beta}$; β is dimensionless; AW is in %.

4.5. Modification of the Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models

Previous research has highlighted the mathematical equivalence of the Bohart–Adams, Thomas, and Yoon–Nelson models [5,6]. As a result, it is possible to modify the Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models in a similar manner to the Bohart–Adams model to account for steric hindrance effects. The original Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models are described by Eqs. (17) and (18), respectively, where η represents the Thomas rate coefficient, G denotes the amount of adsorbed contaminant per unit mass of adsorbent, M represents the adsorbent mass, Q is the volumetric flow rate, and λ and τ are empirical parameters specific to the Yoon–Nelson model. The newly modified Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models, considering the influence of steric hindrance, can be expressed as Eqs. (19) and (20), respectively.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\eta GM/Q - \eta c_0 t)} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\lambda \tau - \lambda t)} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\eta_1 GM/Q - \eta_1 c_0 t) + \exp(-\eta_2 c_0 t)} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\lambda_1 \tau - \lambda_1 t) + \exp(-\lambda_2 t)} \quad (20)$$

In Fig. 7, the diclofenac breakthrough curve, initially presented in Fig. 1, is displayed alongside the model fits obtained from the newly developed Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models. For the new Thomas model, the following parameter values were used: $c_0 = 0.01 \text{ mg cm}^{-3}$, $M = 0.4 \text{ g}$, and $Q = 2 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}$. The new Yoon–Nelson model, like its original formulation, is purely empirical and does not require any system or operational parameters. The parameter estimates and R^2 values for the new Thomas and Yoon–Nelson model fits are summarized in Table 7. As expected, the performance of the new Thomas and Yoon–Nelson models depicted in Fig. 7 was identical to that of the Chu–Hashim model shown in Fig. 1. All three model fits produced an R^2 value of 0.995.

Fig. 7. Fitting diclofenac breakthrough data [7] with the new Thomas model [Eq. (19)] (A) and the new Yoon–Nelson model [Eq. (20)] (B).

Table 7. Parameter estimates and R^2 values for the model fits plotted in Fig. 7.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
New Thomas	(19)	G	133.7 (2.8)	R^2	0.995
		η_1	0.163 (0.01)		
		η_2	0.012 (6.3×10^{-4})		
New Yoon–Nelson	(20)	τ	2674 (56.9)	R^2	0.995
		λ_1	0.002 (0.26)		
		λ_2	1.2×10^{-4} (6.3×10^{-6})		

^a G is in mg g^{-1} ; η_1 and η_2 are in $\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; τ is in min ; λ_1 and λ_2 are in min^{-1} .

5. Conclusions

The Bohart–Adams and Chu–Hashim models were used to describe the tailing breakthrough curves of diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole contaminants. Remarkably, the Chu–Hashim model significantly outperformed the Bohart–Adams model, providing improved representations of both tailing breakthrough curves. The Chu–Hashim model effectively employed two distinct rate coefficients (k_1 and k_2) to capture the sharp initial phase and the gradual tailing portion of the diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole breakthrough data. These tailing characteristics were attributed to steric hindrance effects. In contrast, the Bohart–Adams model, relying on a single rate coefficient, failed to accurately describe the bipartite shape of the breakthrough data, leading to compromises in representing the entire shapes of the diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole breakthrough curves.

Additionally, the Chu–Hashim model showcased its versatility by accurately describing breakthrough data characterized by a high degree of symmetry or a pseudo-hyperbolic curve shape. When compared to a mechanistic model or the empirical Yan model, the Chu–Hashim model clearly demonstrated significant superiority in data fitting. These results highlight its potential for practical applications in designing and optimizing fixed bed adsorbers. As a promising fixed bed model, future research endeavors may focus on further refining and expanding its capabilities to encompass breakthrough curves with diverse shapes and characteristics.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Both authors contributed equally to this work.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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